

Taskforce FAIRification as a service

Summary report

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Purpose of this document

In this report we document and summarize the findings from this taskforce for persons in charge of the Data/Digital Competence Centers of Leiden University and Leiden University Medical Center and their data stewardship community.

Problem description

Making (meta)data more FAIR (hereafter: FAIRification) is key for the success of open science and research reproducibility. It is increasingly required by funders and is part of the data management policy at both Leiden University (LEI) and Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC). Yet, for many it is still unclear where and how to start with FAIRification.

Several FAIRification approaches exist but no Leiden framework for delivering and supporting the use of such approaches is present at the research data management support groups of LEI/LUMC. In addition, approaches differ and are not mapped to the generally accepted research data lifecycle, and required tools often differ in complexity or maturity.

Goal of the taskforce: How to do FAIR(ification)?

We focused on two approaches that originated in Leiden, namely a generic workflow for the data FAIRification process [1] and the GO FAIR Three-Point FAIRification Framework [2]. The goal of the taskforce was to explore if and how these approaches could be offered as LEI/LUMC services to researchers.

Taskforce way of working

We met monthly for online brainstorm sessions over the course of about six months.

Results

On the next pages we summarize our findings:

1. Comparison of the abovementioned FAIRification approaches
2. Related developments
3. Pitch deck for a course/training 'FAIRification through the Research Data Life Cycle'
4. Overview of FAIRification tools, FAIR & the research data lifecycle
5. Identified issues and questions on the go
6. Thoughts for local Data/Digital Competence Centers (DCC's)

1. Comparison FAIRification approaches

Several FAIRification approaches exist. We analyzed two that originated in Leiden and that we were familiar with to some extent:

- **The generic FAIRification workflow** [1] emerged from numerous "Bring Your Own Data" (BYOD) workshops [3] and FAIRification projects of rare disease patient registries [4]. It is a step-by-step workflow to be performed in a multidisciplinary team.

- **The Three-Point FAIRification Framework** [2] offers three means to guide a community through the FAIR landscape. It consists of 1) Formulating domain-relevant metadata requirements and making these metadata machine-actionable through Metadata-for-Machine (M4M)-workshops; 2) Creating a FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) to document the choices made regarding each of the FAIR guiding principles; and 3) Deploying the metadata in a FAIR Data Point.

1.1 Quick comparison

These two approaches are probably complementary to each other, but a quick comparison reveals that both approaches:

- Share the requirement of a multidisciplinary team effort to make (a part of) the (meta)data more FAIR. Thus, both approaches regard FAIRification as a ‘team sport’
- Are not meant for describing steps a single researcher can take to make (meta)data more FAIR. Of course, single researchers can also take action to make their (meta)data more FAIR, but the abovementioned approaches do not provide practical pointers for this
- Are not mapped to the research data lifecycle which is often used by research data management support groups to guide researchers through data management / stewardship requirements
- Differ in methods, tools and ‘FAIR-language’ used. For example:
 - Generic FAIRification workflow: *semantic models, ontologies, linked data, triple stores, Openrefine, Protégé, about metadata and/or data (depending on objective)*
 - Three-Point FAIRification Framework: *controlled vocabularies, FIP’s, CEDAR, nanopublications, about metadata*
- Do not necessarily cover all FAIR subprinciples during one FAIRification iteration so that from the start choices should be made about the scope of the FAIRification
- Can be about prospective and retrospective FAIRification
- Usually have a large FAIR training or awareness component

1.2 Metadata FAIRification

To implement FAIRification as a service we focused on metadata because the FAIR principles are to a large extent about metadata, and FAIRification of metadata might be somewhat less subject to privacy and security considerations than FAIRification of data and therefore easier to implement. Still, the FAIRification of metadata is a very broad and complex spectrum to cover and is nonetheless subject to careful privacy and security considerations. Services may be offered along several axes:

- **Metadata for discoverability, for accessibility, for reusability.** The FAIR principles require different types of metadata. For example, principle F2 is mainly about metadata for discoverability. Principle R1 and R1.2 are mainly about metadata for describing the context and provenance. A FAIRification service could target only one or give ‘the client’ options to choose from.
- **From minimally required metadata to rich metadata.** The FAIR principles require ‘rich’ metadata and ‘detailed’ provenance information, but it is hard to generally define what is ‘rich’ and ‘detailed’. A FAIRification service could first advise about minimally required metadata to improve findability (e.g., citation metadata) and minimally required metadata to improve provenance information, in a machine-actionable way, before delving deeper into more detailed or community-specific metadata.

- **From human-readable metadata to machine-actionable metadata.** Often the FAIR journey starts with descriptions on what certain variables mean, what are the access conditions, what were the protocols followed, etc. Even though such textual descriptions and documentation may not be considered part of the FAIR principles itself, these are steps towards FAIR and machine-actionability. The 5-star scheme for linked open data [5] proposed by Tim Berners-Lee may provide a guideline for moving from human-readable to machine-actionable metadata (although for FAIR metadata it should be adapted, and FAIR is not the same as Open):

<https://5stardata.info/en/>.

1.3 Requirements for implementation as LEI/LUMC service

- Merge the (or other) approaches, choose one of them, or offer both if serving different purposes
- Define explicit and concrete outcomes of the service, time investment, costs, and timeline so that research groups or communities know what to expect
- Have IT-systems in place to host FAIRification tools and their resulting FAIRified (meta)data or models OR adapt the service to the systems that are available within the organization
- Offer different levels/types of FAIRification services varying in complexity, time investment and 'client' (e.g., single researcher vs. community)
- Bundle this information in a brochure or flyer for communication purposes
- Have data stewards trained in 1) guiding the process; 2) required tools; 3) metadata modelling with ontologies

2. Related developments @ LEI/LUMC

FAIRification as a service could involve several components, e.g., offering certain tools, workshops, trainings, advice and/or providing practical information. The following developments are currently underway at LEI and/or LUMC.

2.1 The “what and how” of metadata (LUMC)

Within the LUMC-project ‘Implementation of the Research Data Management Guidelines’ (LUMC [intranet](#)) we are working on adding metadata information to the ‘LUMC Guideline Research Data Stewardship’ and the related ‘Standard Operating Procedure Data Life Cycle’.

2.2 Analyzing and mapping different FAIRification workflows (LUMC)

Various other workflows for making (meta)data FAIR exist, such as the [FAIRopoly guidance](#) for the European Joint Program on Rare Diseases, another [GO-FAIR process](#), or the [FAIRplus FAIRification Framework](#). We are involved in a Health RI project to identify the overlap and differences between these workflows, and what would be needed to implement such a workflow at a local organization.

2.3 FAIRification workflow pilot (LUMC)

For the Leiden Longevity Study we recently followed the steps of the generic workflow for the Data FAIRification Process. We documented our experiences in [Github](#).

2.4 DMP-FIP mapping (LEI)

Mapping the LEI data management plan to FAIR Implementation profiles is an ongoing project together with the GO FAIR Foundation and the DS Wizard tool development team. More information can be found in the related [article](#).

2.5 Nanopublications as a FAIR data publishing service (LEI)

Researchers and data stewards at the Science faculty at LEI are modelling nanopublications together with the GO FAIR Foundation to investigate the possibility to provide nanopublications to publish FAIR data.

2.6 FAIR YODA for communities (LEI)

LEI is part of the FAIR YODA for Communities project coordinated by SURF to store and publish FAIR data.

3. Pitch deck for a course/training ‘FAIRification through the Data Life Cycle’

In a separate slide deck we present our ideas about a course or workshop series that aims to help researchers and data stewards to better understand the possible FAIRification approaches, related tools, importance of metadata and how this maps to the research data lifecycle. This slide deck is available on request.

4. FAIRification tools, FAIR & the Data Life Cycle

During the FAIRification process many tools can be considered, some more mature than others, some very much tied into semantic web technologies. In the separate slide deck we showed how these tools and the FAIR principles may be mapped to the Data Life Cycle.

4.1 A non-exhaustive list of FAIRification tools

See also slide deck.

Tools

CEDAR <https://metadatacenter.org>

RightField <https://rightfield.org.uk>

Ontop <https://ontop-vkg.org>

Nanobench <https://github.com/peta-pico/nanobench>

OpenRefine <https://openrefine.org>

FAIR Data Point <https://www.fairdatapoint.org>

YODA <https://servicedesk.surf.nl/wiki/display/WIKI/Yoda+Hosting>

Zenodo <https://zenodo.org>

4TU <https://www.4tu.nl>

DANS Data Station: Life, Health and Medical Sciences <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/data-stations/life-health-and-medical-sciences/>

Dataverse <https://dataverse.nl>

FIP Wizard <https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org>

Protégé <https://protege.stanford.edu/>

Ontology Lookup Service <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/index>

4.2 FAIRification tools and FAIR steps mapped to the Data Life Cycle

See also slide deck.

5. Identified issues and questions on the go

The table below shows a selection of issues regarding FAIR(ification) or metadata that we identified by talking to other researchers and data stewards at LEI/LUMC. Note that some of the tools mentioned might be specific for either LEI or LUMC.

Issue, question, challenge	Perspective
<i>"I am advised to generate some high-level metadata with the Dublin Core generator, export this as an xml- or json-file and store it locally on a network-drive where my research data are also stored. What is the point of that?"</i>	Researcher
<i>"I invested a lot of time annotating data in Castor, but I don't see the advantage of my effort, neither for myself nor for others."</i>	Researcher
<i>"I understand the 'what' of FAIR, but not the 'how'. How can I make my (meta)data more FAIR as an individual PhD-student? What are simple steps I can perform as a PhD-student?"</i>	Researcher
<i>"I have to fill out the same high-level metadata in different (administrative) systems, for example in DMP-online, for project administration, in CEDAR, in Castor, etc. This feels like double or triple work."</i>	Researcher
<i>"Why do we spend so much time in semantically modelling 'simple' variables like gender and age? It cannot be that no one else did that before."</i>	Researcher
<i>"What's in it for me to spend all this time making my data FAIR if that's time I cannot then spend publishing more papers while my peers will do the bare minimum to comply, thereby having more time to publish more papers and get awarded more funding as a result."</i>	Researcher
<i>"Can you tell me how FAIR my data files are? Or which data format meets the FAIR principles?"</i>	Researcher

<i>"Many levels/types of metadata exist, from high level citation metadata such as the title, creator and description of a dataset to detailed and/or community specific metadata at the data level. It is not clear to me for what level/type of metadata a FAIR Data Point (FDP) or M4M-workshop is."</i>	Data steward
<i>"Regarding FAIR-principle F1: Funder or internal project numbers are often not globally unique and persistent. Should they be globally unique and persistent, and if so, how to deal with that?"</i>	Data steward
<i>"To some extent we can help a research team or project to generate machine-actionable, FAIR metadata, but we don't have the IT infrastructure in place to host such metadata, so why bother researchers with it at this moment?"</i>	Data steward
<i>"Quite some tools/services are in place at LUMC and LU that produce metadata, such as YODA, Dataverse, Electronic Lab Notebook, Castor, Panama. How to use/integrate the metadata produced by those tools/services efficiently?"</i>	Data steward
<i>"At the moment how does one link and nest nanopublications in reality? It can easily get out of hand with a lot of data to keep track of."</i>	Data steward
Issue, question, challenge	FAIR principle
<i>"Are GUID's, UUID's, DOI's, PURLS, IRI's and URI's always persistent?"</i>	F1
<i>"How do I generate such identifiers (besides when a data repository generates one for me)?"</i>	F1
<i>"How do I know if a certain URL is a globally unique and persistent identifier?"</i>	F1
<i>"Is the DOI a data repository generates for me an identifier for my dataset or for my metadata?"</i>	F1
<i>"Which options does LEI/LUMC currently have to make my metadata findable in a machine-actionable way?"</i>	F2
<i>"Which searchable resources are available for researchers for a) metadata; b) data, and how do I know if this resource is 'searchable' or not?"</i>	F4
<i>"Which protocols pertaining to accessibility are currently operational for LEI/LUMC researchers?"</i>	A1, A1.1, A1.2
<i>"Should (meta)data be represented preferably in RDF or JSON-LD?"</i>	I1
<i>"Does principle I2 imply that we should not use vocabularies like SNOMED CT or LOINC?"</i>	I2
<i>"I understand that data should be associated with detailed provenance, but how can I associate metadata with detailed provenance?"</i>	R1.2
<i>"Does LEI/LUMC provide a general or minimal implementation of machine-actionable provenance information?"</i>	R1.2

6. Recommendations for LEI/LUMC Data/Digital Competence Centers (DCCs)

- **Have a local DCC FAIR roadmap or DCC FAIR implementation plan.** The lack of a concrete FAIR roadmap or implementation plan is a barrier when an organization wants to embrace the FAIR Principles [6]: it is unclear which steps an organization must take, what the required efforts and costs are, what the expected turnaround time is, and what the incentive or reward is. It would be good if a DCC has such a roadmap or implementation plan in alignment with existing data management policies and protocols at the institutional and disciplinary level, respectively.
- **Involve the IT-department.** Some FAIR tools are not mature or maintained, are heavily tied into semantic web technology or not implemented within the LEI/LUMC technical infrastructure. To implement and integrate such tools dedicated IT staff is needed, skilled in semantic web and linked data technology.
- **Allow small steps towards FAIR.** Describing or documenting in human terms, for example, what are the conditions for data access or what the informed consent form says about data reusability may not strictly pertain to one of the FAIR (sub)principles, but it is a step towards machine-actionable FAIRness. Similarly, some relatively simple machine-actionable steps could be taken.
- **Provide training to go hand in hand with tooling.** This is true for all tooling but maybe even more so for FAIR tooling since there is still a large educational component to FAIR data.
- **Have an eye for the researcher's perspective and have a clear message about expectations and outlook for researchers when participating in a FAIRification trajectory.** Regarding FAIR we often hear the expression that 'we are building the plane while flying it' and researchers are involved in this development. This has pros and cons. Some researchers may like to be at the forefront of such cutting-edge developments; others may just like to have practical pointers to make (meta)data more FAIR with user-friendly tools readily available within and supported by the organization. At a minimum it would be fair to be transparent and clear to researchers about the stage of development, what is in place and what is not, what is expected from them and when they can get help from data stewards.
- **Make clear that, for now, FAIRification is a multidisciplinary team effort and an (experimental) design process.** Different types of expertise are needed to carry out FAIRification [1]. At a minimum a team should have a data steward with expertise of the FAIRification procedure, a data steward or researcher with expertise of the local environment and domain of research, and a software engineer who can develop or implement the software needed for FAIRifying and managing the (FAIRified) data. From the start privacy and security experts should be involved, but these experts don't need to be part of the core team necessarily. As mentioned above FAIRification is still often 'building the plane while flying' and in that sense it is a design process where understanding, definitions and solutions of the problem are constantly adapted to the information at hand.

References

1. Generic Workflow for the Data FAIRification Process
https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00028
2. Three-Point FAIRification Framework <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/>
3. Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) workshops <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3207809>
4. Towards FAIRification of Sensitive and Fragmented Rare Disease Patient Data
<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1572508/v1>
5. 5-star linked open data <https://5stardata.info/en/>
6. Onderzoek naar de stimulering van FAIR Principes bij de overheid
<https://forumstandaardisatie.nl/sites/default/files/FS/2021/0421/FS-20210421.4E-Onderzoek-FAIR-Data-Principes-Innovalor.pdf>

See slide deck (available on request) for further references.

